

HIRATSUKA, Lúcia. **Histórias guardadas pelo rio** [Stories kept by the river]. Illustrations Lúcia Hiratsuka. São Paulo: SM, 2018.

REVIEW¹

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Fishing and trading stories are common practices in that city. Stories are exchanged, presented as gifts, collected, embroidered. However, no matter how hard he tries, Pedro is unable to catch them and decides to uncover the secret of such a practice. Author and illustrator Lúcia Hiratsuka hence brings the reader a hamper filled with fished-out stories. She is the recipient of major awards, such as the Prêmio Jabuti for Illustration and the Prêmio FNLIJ, having also been included in the White Ravens catalogue, put together by the International Youth Library in Munich, and in the FNLIJ-IBBY 2016 list of honours.

Keywords: Oral history. Creativity. Regionalism.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2019 Bologna. Books published in 2018 and reviewed in 2019. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

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